

Table 1. Occurrence of aflatoxin in rough rice and processed rice in India.

Commodity	State	Year	Samples analyzed (no.)	Positive for aflatoxin (no.)	Aflatoxin concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)
Rough rice	Andhra Pradesh	1975	272	Nil	-
Rough rice ^a	Andhra Pradesh	1976	80	10	Trace-430
Rough rice ^a	Andhra Pradesh	1977	81	19	30-1130
Rice, raw	Karnataka	1974	35	0	-
Rice, raw	Karnataka	1981	76	4	Trace-120
	Uttar Pradesh				
	Andhra Pradesh				
Rice, raw	Andhra Pradesh	1983	63	0	-
Rice, raw	Andhra Pradesh	1987	64	0	-
Parboiled rice	Karnataka	1974	25	8	0-50
Parboiled rice	Tamil Nadu	1976	18	7	30-130
	Thanjavur				
Parboiled rice	Andhra Pradesh	1981	77	7	Trace-120
Parboiled rice	Andhra Pradesh	1988	22	3	Trace- 10

^aAffected by cyclones.

cyclones along the coastal region of Andhra Pradesh in 1976, 12.5% of 80 samples were positive for aflatoxin; 8.7% had levels from 0.08 to 0.43 ppm. The dominant mycoflora was *Aspergillus flavus*. In 1977, higher aflatoxin levels were found in cyclone-damaged rice: in 81 samples, 23.5% were positive for aflatoxin with 0.03-1.13 ppm levels.

Aflatoxin contamination can be even higher in parboiled rice. Levels

reported ranged from traces to 0.13 ppm.

In studies on the effect of processing, dehusking removed 50-70% of the toxin. Polishing further reduced toxin content to 20-35%. Parboiling reduced toxin content in already infected rice by 50%; dehusking and polishing reduced toxins 7 and 17% more (Table 2).

Rice is a dietary staple in many Asian countries, and consumption of mold-damaged or contaminated rice

Table 2. Aflatoxin content of rough and raw rice after processing.

Treatment	Aflatoxin content (ppm)		
	Masuri	Jaya	Sona
Infected rough rice	53.5	16.2	13.3
Infected rough rice after dehusking	24.0	7.6	4.4
Infected rough rice after dehusking and polishing (10%)	18.8	5.7	2.6
Infected rough rice after parboiling	17.9	9.2	8.1
Infected rough rice after parboiling and dehusking	10.4	5.0	3.1
Infected rough rice after parboiling, dehusking, and polishing	3.5	4.5	2.1

can present serious hazards to public health. Drying to safe moisture levels before storage is an important step. ' In natural disaster situations, the need to monitor stored rice for aflatoxins increases; parboiled rice should be monitored even under normal conditions. □

SOCIOECONOMIC IMPACT

Production

Constraints to adoption of rice technology in West Bengal, India

N. K. Saha, Joint Director of Agriculture (Rural Sociology), Government of West Bengal; and D. Panda, Research Associate, Farming Systems Research, R.K.M. Ashrama, Narendrapur, South 24-Parganas, West Bengal, India

We studied five villages in Burdwan district under the Operational Research Project on Rice, to identify constraints to adoption of high-yielding wet season rice varieties. The project area has 2,543.76 cultivated ha and is within the irrigation command of

Damodar canal system. Of 3,022 farmers, only 1,073 actually have direct control over agricultural activities.

We used stratified random sampling to select 270 working farmers for the study.

Constraints identified were the following:

Holdings in general were small, segmented, and scattered in different locations in more than one village. Much labor is wasted in the movement of inputs, implements, and produce. Farmers have difficulty supervising all their plots efficiently. Consequently, average yield and net return are low (Table 1).

Irrigation water provided by the Damodar canal system cannot be regulated to fit the varying water

Table 1. Plots owned by rice farmers in Burdwan, West Bengal, India, 1982.

Plots (no.)/ farmer	Yield (t/ha)	Cost (\$/ha)	Return (\$/ha)
1-3	3.1	271.5	128.0
4-6	3.0	283.3	100.0
7-9	2.9	288.3	93.0
10-12	2.8	291.6	73.3
13-15	2.8	303.3	63.3
>15	2.7	308.2	52.1

requirements of transplanted wet season rice at different growth stages. Minimum flow through the existing water canal is 5 ft³/s, a supply that often is detrimental to the crop.

Puffed rice is an essential component of daily life for the people of this area. Puffed rice prepared from traditional varieties, such as Daharna-

era and Kalma, is superior to that prepared from modern high-yielding varieties such as Pankaj and Ratna.

Most of the high-yielding varieties (except Pankaj and Masuri) produce short straw not suitable as cattle feed or roofing material. Marginal and small farmers need straw to thatch their huts.

Nonfarming landowners control 33% of the land. They live outside the project area and either hire labor or rent the land to sharecroppers who take little interest in changing their cropping practices. Moreover, 49.2% of the farm families belong to economi-

cally and socially backward scheduled caste and 1.5% to scheduled tribal communities. Most members of these families work as agricultural laborers and sharecroppers and do not have any control over production decisions. All these factors hamper the acceptance of high-yielding varieties (Table 2).

Cultivation costs more for high-yielding varieties than for traditional ones. The marginal and small farmers, 85% of the farming households, cannot afford to grow high-yielding varieties, even though they are aware of the potential of such varieties. Adequate institutional credit is not easily avail-

Table 2. Area planted to high-yielding varieties by scheduled caste and by absentee owners compared to others. Burdwan, West Bengal, India, 1982.

Farmer category	% of area planted to modern varieties
Scheduled caste or scheduled tribe	11.6
Absentee owner	15.4
Other farmers	73.0

able, particularly from the nationalized banks and cooperatives operating in the area. □

ANNOUNCEMENTS

First multilingual agricultural research CD-ROM released

Food, agriculture, and science, the first release in a series that will eventually constitute a full, 6,000-title, agricultural library on CD-ROM, is now available from the secretariat of the Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research (CGIAR). The new CD-ROM disk is accompanied by trilingual aids in English, French, and Spanish on floppy disks.

Documents reproduced in *Food agriculture, and science* are drawn from 20 international agricultural research centers—one document per center—and cover 4,000 pages with 850 illustrations, all of which are on the CD-ROM disk.

Among the titles included are *A farmer's primer on growing rice*, *Field problems of beans in Latin America*, *Potato research*, *Agriculture-aquaculture farming systems*, *Trends and projections of food in the third world*, and *Sorghum breeding*.

The new CD-ROM is a prototype, which will be tried out internationally. It will be distributed free to interested institutions in developing countries by International agricultural research centers, and will be sold in the U.S. for \$99

from Knowledge Access International, Mountain View, CA 94043.

Development of the CD-ROM library is sponsored by the CGIAR, an informal association of over 40 countries, international and regional organizations, and private foundations established in 1971 to support a system of agricultural research around the world. The World Bank, the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization, and the United Nations Development Programme are co-sponsors of the CGIAR.

The proprietary software technology used in the production of *Food, agriculture, and science*—KAware DISK PUBLISHER and KAware2 RETRIEVAL SYSTEM—is from Knowledge Access International, a leading producer of CD-ROM, WORM, and floppy disk “desktop databases” for business, research, and the professions.

For more information, contact CGIAR c/o World Bank, 1818 H Street, N.W., Room N5063, Washington, D.C. 20433, USA. (202) 334-8031 or Knowledge Access International, 2685 Marine Way, Suite 1305, Mountain View, California 94043, USA. 800/2KAware or 415/969-0606.

IRRC 90 set

The theme of the International Rice Research Conference 1990, to be held in Seoul, Korea, 27-31 August, is IRRIGATED RICE. IRRI and the Rural Development Administration, Korea, are collaborating to organize IRRC 90.

Overview papers and discussion will focus on factors that limit higher yield potential and on the attendant problems of grain quality, distribution, and marketing.

Most of the world's rice supply is grown in the irrigated areas, and irrigated rice shows the highest yield potential. Increasing world populations and limited growth in irrigation mean that grain yield potentials must be increased to 13-15 t/ha.

Low temperature and blast disease are two factors that limit high and stable rice yields. Increasingly, irrigated rice farmers are practicing direct seeding for crop establishment. More related issues will be taken up by conference participants.

Rice scientists from Asia, Africa, Europe, Australia and Latin America will be participating in the conference. □